
Policy-based Remote User Authentication from Multi-biometrics

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In this paper, we introduce the first generic framework of policy-based remote user authentication from multiple biometrics. The proposed framework allows an authorized user to remotely authenticate herself to an authentication server using her multiple biometrics, which enhances both the security and usability of user authentications. The authentication server approves a user's authentication request if and only if the user's multiple biometrics satisfies an authentication policy. In particular, the authentication policy can be dynamically updated to satisfy different security and usability requirements in practice. We implement an instantiation of the proposed framework and report its performance under various authentication policies.

Keywords: Remote User Authentication, Multi-biometrics, Authentication Policy

1. INTRODUCTION

Biometric-based remote user authentication (BRUA) has been widely used in many real-life applications, such as e-commerce and mobile commerce. The benefit of using biometrics over traditional password is obvious. It is challenging for people to remember many secure passwords for various accounts and updating passwords frequently for security reasons. Since a user's biometrics data is permanently and uniquely associated with the user, it is convenient to use biometrics for user authentication.

The entropy of authentication credentials is essential to user authentication. Undoubtedly, low entropy of authentication credentials leads to low security of user authentication. In the real world, unfortunately, most authentication credentials that are commonly used are of low-entropy. For example, a study shows that only 33.6 percent of fingerprints are unique among 2,067,942 ($\approx 2^{21}$) fingerprints collected from one of the top 15 French websites [1]. Consequently, a user with "close-enough" fingerprints may impersonate a target user for authentication. While there exist high-entropy biometrics such as DNA, the biometrics that belong to the low-entropy category (e.g., fingerprint, face, and iris) are widely used in practice due to the ease of measurement [2].

Many have proposed to increase the entropy of biometrics in user authentication by using multiple biometrics. It is stated that a fusion strategy

combining information from multiple biometrics can achieve sufficient entropy for user authentication [3, 4]. If user authentication is performed by combining multiple biometrics in an AND manner, a potential problem of this solution is higher false rejection rate (low usability) as measured against legitimate users, at the price of better entropy/security as measured against impersonators. It is possible some of a user's multiple biometrics get weaker or damaged due to aging or errors. It is thus better to use both AND and OR in combining and managing multiple biometrics in user authentication so as to increase flexibility and balance between entropy/security and false rejection/usability as needed in practice.

In this work, we design a policy-based remote user authentication scheme using multi-biometrics (PBRUA). In PBRUA, user authentication is performed in a fine-grained manner, which is analogous to the attribute-based access control [5], where users are tagged by biometrics (i.e., attributes). An authentication decision is made by an authentication server evaluating an authentication policy on a set of biometrics associated with the same user. For instance, assume that user Alice has associated biometrics $\{A, B, C, D\}$, and that authentication server Bob enforces policy $(A \text{ AND } B) \text{ OR } (C \text{ AND } D)$. In this case, Alice can be authenticated by Bob successfully, as Bob's policy is satisfied by Alice's biometrics. We note that the authentication policy should be updatable according to the application context, in which security

FIGURE 1. Overview of user authentications. The subfigure on top illustrates user authentication based on a single biometrics, while the subfigure on bottom shows the policy-based user authentication from multiple biometrics. Alice is an enrolled user, and server Bob maintains a database to store information from all enrolled users, including user ID, sketches, PKs, and DK (subfigure on bottom).

and usability requirements may change over time.

Our Contributions. We introduce a new framework for remote user authentication to be performed in a secure, flexible, and fine-grained manner. The major contributions of this work are summarized as follows.

- *New Construction.* We introduce the first generic framework of policy-based remote user authentication from multiple biometrics (PBRUA) for user authentication to be performed in a fine-grained manner. A unique feature of this framework is that it allows user authentication to have the enhanced security and usability simultaneously.
- *Secure and Flexible.* The proposed PBRUA achieves user authenticity even if attackers can access a certain number of user’s biometrics. The authentication policy specified by authentication server can be dynamically updated according to different security and usability requirements in practice.
- *Practical Instantiation.* We present an instantiation of PBRUA and validate its practicality. The performance overhead of our instantiation is reasonably low in our experiments.

2. OVERVIEW

In this section, we provide an overview of PBRUA. Figure 1 illustrates our proposed framework, where a fuzzy extractor is used to convert repeated noisy readings of the same biometrics into the same key of uniform distribution, and a secure sketch (i.e., an

“encrypted” form of biometrics) is used to recover the original biometrics from nearby biometrics [6]. Specifically, Alice relies on her enrolled sketch stored at the server side to derive a secret key for generating a digital signature on the combination of challenge nonce and response nonce (i.e., message), then Bob verifies the message-signature pair under Alice’s enrolled public key. Note that no information is stored locally at the user side, and no biometrics is stored in plaintext at the server side.

Our proposed PBRUA requires Alice to generate multiple sketches and public keys during enrollment. The most suitable cryptographic primitive that allows a fine-grained authentication control on multiple sketches and public keys is key-policy attribute-based encryption KP-ABE [7]. Applying KP-ABE, authentication server Bob can enforce an authentication policy over Alice’s enrolled public keys. Alice’s ciphertext on a message (which consists of the exchanged nonce) is associated with a set of derived public keys, in which the derived public keys must satisfy the authentication policy for successful authentication.

Consider the case in which two biometrics A (i.e., w_a) and B (i.e., w_b) are used by Alice for user authentication according to an authentication policy. Alice first derives two key pairs (sk_a, pk_a) , (sk_b, pk_b) from her biometrics (w_a, w_b) and the enrolled sketches. Then, Alice generates a message-signature pair using signing key SK , which “aggregates” the derived secret keys (sk_a, sk_b) , and generates a KP-ABE ciphertext on a chosen nonce under the derived public keys (pk_a, pk_b) . On the server-side, Bob decrypts the nonce if the authentication policy is satisfied by the derived public keys (pk_a, pk_b) , and verifies the message-signature pair under Alice’s verification key PK , which “aggregates” the derived public keys (pk_a, pk_b) . Successful verification requires that the derived public keys (pk_a, pk_b) satisfy the authentication policy under the enrolled decryption key DK . For convenience, we call DK authentication policy key in this paper, which is a decryption key in KP-ABE. Note that all enrolled users in the system may share the same authentication policy, but their authentication policy keys are different.

The proposed PBRUA has the following unique features. First, Alice can successfully authenticate herself to Bob even if some of her biometrics are temporarily unavailable at the time of user authentication as long as the authentication policy is satisfied. For example, consider authentication policy $(A \text{ AND } B) \text{ OR } (C \text{ AND } D)$. It is sufficient for Alice to use biometrics A and B only to perform user authentication, while biometrics C and D remain unused. Second, the authentication server can easily update the authentication policy in various contexts without interacting with the enrolled users. Now, we present the commonly used notations (see Table 1) in this paper.

TABLE 1. Summary of notations

Notation	Definition
$(\mathbf{sk}_i, \mathbf{pk}_i)$	User i 's secret/public key
$(\mathbf{SK}, \mathbf{PK})$	User's signing/verification key
(R_i, P_i)	User i 's secret value/public sketch
$(\mathbf{msk}, \mathbf{mpk})$	Server's master secret/public key
ID	User's identity information
$\text{dist}(w, w')$	Distance between biometrics w and w'
$t \in \mathbb{R}^+$	Threshold value (positive real number)
(δ, Λ)	A set of attributes/an authentication policy
(n_0, n_1)	The transmitted challenge/response nonce

3. PRELIMINARIES

In this section, we present some building blocks, including fuzzy extractors and attribute-based encryptions, which are used in our proposed construction.

3.1. Fuzzy Extractors

Fuzzy extractors (FE) can convert a non-uniform data (e.g., biometrics) to a uniformly random value. The converted value can be used in generating a cryptographic key for user authentications. FE usually works with secure sketch SS . The SS will take user's biometrics w as input, and output a sketch P . In addition, the SS relies on error correcting techniques to recover w from P if a nearby biometrics w' is statistically (or computationally) close to w . We notice that the sketch P can be viewed as an "encryption" of w , where decryption works from any close w' . We stress that the sketch P is a public value as it does not disclose w unless w' is given. The definition of SS is shown below [6].

Let \mathcal{M} be a metric space on N points with a distance function $\text{dist} : \mathcal{M} \times \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+ = [0, \infty)$, where $N = |\mathcal{M}|$.

DEFINITION 3.1. A secure sketch includes two procedures (SS , Rec).

- SS : It takes a biometrics $w \in \mathcal{M}$ as input, outputs a sketch $P \in \{0, 1\}^*$.
- Rec : It takes a nearby biometrics $w' \in \mathcal{M}$ and the sketch $P \in \{0, 1\}^*$ as input, outputs w if $\text{dist}(w, w') \leq t$.

Informally, a fuzzy extractor obtains a secret value R (i.e., a uniform string with fixed length l) from $w \in \mathcal{M}$. Later, R can be recovered from a given input w' if w and w' are close. The formal definition is given below [6].

DEFINITION 3.2. A fuzzy extractor includes two procedures (Gen , Rep).

- Gen : It takes a biometrics $w \in \mathcal{M}$ as input, outputs a secret value $R \in \{0, 1\}^l$ and a public sketch $P \in \{0, 1\}^*$, where

$$(R, P) \leftarrow \text{Gen}(w).$$

- Rep : It takes a nearby biometrics $w' \in \mathcal{M}$ and the sketch $P \in \{0, 1\}^*$ as input, outputs R , where

$$R \leftarrow \text{Rep}(w', P) \text{ if } \text{dist}(w, w') \leq t.$$

Remark. A secure sketch is designed to help an enrolled user to recover secret values from her noisy data. In this work, we use multiple secure sketches to hide a user's enrolled biometrics $\{w\}$ during enrollment. In the case of user authentication, we allow the enrolled user to recover secret values $\{R\}$ by employing multiple fuzzy extractors on her nearby biometrics $\{w'\}$. The recovered $\{R\}$ can be used in generating a cryptographic key to secure user authentications.

3.2. Attribute-Based Encryptions

Bilinear Maps. Let (g, h) be two group generators. The group generation is defined as follows: $(q, \mathbb{G}, \mathbb{H}, \mathbb{G}_T, \hat{e}) \leftarrow \text{GroupGen}(1^\lambda)$, where λ is a security parameter, q is a prime number, \mathbb{G}, \mathbb{H} and \mathbb{G}_T are cyclic groups of order q , and $\hat{e} : \mathbb{G} \times \mathbb{H} \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_T$ is an asymmetric bilinear map.

Access Structure. Let $\{P_1, \dots, P_n\}$ be a set of parties. A collection $\Lambda \subseteq 2^{\{P_1, \dots, P_n\}}$ is monotone if $\forall B, C : \text{if } B \in \Lambda \text{ and } B \subseteq C \text{ then } C \in \Lambda$. An access structure is a collection of non-empty subsets of $\{P_1, \dots, P_n\}$ (i.e., $\Lambda \subseteq 2^{\{P_1, \dots, P_n\}} \setminus \{\emptyset\}$). The sets in Λ are called authorized sets, and the sets not in Λ are called unauthorized sets.

Monotone Span Programs (MSPs). Let δ be an attribute universe. A secret-sharing scheme Π with domain of secrets realizing an access structure Λ on δ is called linear if: 1) The shares of a secret s for each attribute form a vector. 2) For each access structure Λ on δ , there exists a matrix \mathbf{M} with n_1 rows and n_2 columns called the share-generating matrix for Π . For $i = 1, \dots, n_1$, we define a function π labels row i of \mathbf{M} with attribute $\pi(i)$ from the attribute universe δ . If we consider the column vector $\vec{v} = (s, r_2, \dots, r_{n_2})$, where s is the secret to be shared and r_2, \dots, r_{n_2} are chosen at random. Then, $\mathbf{M}\vec{v}$ is the vector of n_1 shares of the secret s according to Π . The share $(\mathbf{M}\vec{v})_j$ belongs to attribute $\pi(j)$, such that $j \in [n_2]$.

According to [8], every linear secret-sharing scheme has the linear reconstruction property. Suppose Π is a MSP for the access structure Λ , $\delta' \in \Lambda$ is an authorized set and let $I \subseteq \{1, 2, \dots, n_1\}$ be $I = \{i \in [n_1] \wedge \pi(i) \in \delta'\}$. There exists the constants $\{\gamma_i \in \mathbb{Z}_q\}_{i \in I}$ such that for any valid shares $\{\lambda_i = (\mathbf{M}\vec{v})_i\}_{i \in I}$ of a secret s according to Π , $\sum_{i \in I} \gamma_i \lambda_i = s$. Besides, these constants $\{\gamma_i\}_{i \in I}$ can be found in polynomial time in the size of the share-generating matrix \mathbf{M} . Note that there is no such $\{\gamma_i\}$ exists for any unauthorized set.

Key-Policy Attribute-Based Encryption. It consists of the following algorithms: KP-ABE=(Setup, KG, Enc, Dec).

- **Setup:** It takes a security parameter λ as input, outputs a master key pair (msk, mpk) .
- **KG:** It takes the master secret key msk and an access structure Λ as input, outputs a decryption key dk .
- **Enc:** It takes the master public key mpk , a message m , and a set of attributes δ as input, outputs a ciphertext C .
- **Dec:** It takes the master public key mpk , a ciphertext C , and the decryption key dk as input, outputs the message m if $\Lambda(\delta) = 1$.

DEFINITION 3.3. *The NM-CCA2 (non-malleability under adaptive chosen ciphertext attack) experiment between a probabilistic polynomial-time (PPT) adversary \mathcal{A} and a challenger \mathcal{S} is defined below.*

$Exp_{\text{ABE}}^{\text{NM-CCA2}}(\lambda)$
 $(\text{mpk}, \text{msk}) \leftarrow \text{Setup}(1^\lambda), b \leftarrow \{0, 1\}$
 $(m_0, m_1, \delta^*) \leftarrow \mathcal{A}^{\mathcal{O}^{\text{KG}}, \mathcal{O}^{\text{Dec}}}(\text{mpk})$
where $dk \leftarrow \mathcal{O}^{\text{KG}}(\text{msk}, \Lambda), m \leftarrow \mathcal{O}^{\text{Dec}}(\text{msk}, C)$
 $C^* \leftarrow \text{Enc}(\text{mpk}, \delta^*, m_b)$
 $b' = \mathcal{A}^{\mathcal{O}^{\text{KG}}, \mathcal{O}^{\text{Dec}}}(C^*)$
If $b' = b$, *return* 1; *else, return* 0

In the experiment, \mathcal{A} is not allowed to query \mathcal{O}^{Dec} on the challenge ciphertext C^ , and the challenge attributes set satisfies $\Lambda(\delta^*) \neq 1$. We define the advantage of \mathcal{A} as*

$$\text{Adv}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\text{NM-CCA2}}(\lambda) = |\Pr[\mathcal{S} \rightarrow 1] - 1/2|.$$

The KP-ABE scheme is NM-CCA2 secure if $\text{Adv}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\text{NM-CCA2}}(\lambda)$ is negligible in λ for any PPT adversary \mathcal{A} .

Remark. We remark that NM-CCA2 security is equal to IND-CCA2 (indistinguishability under adaptive chosen ciphertext attack) security [9]. The non-malleability states that, given an encryption of plaintext on m , it is impossible to generate another ciphertext which decrypts to $f(m)$ without learning m , where f is a publicly known function. We note that non-malleability is an essential property in user authentication to thwart tampering. Without it, an attacker can impersonate a honest user by modifying the previously-generated ciphertext. The NM-CCA2 security of KP-ABE is used to prove the security of the proposed construction.

4. DEFINITION AND MODEL

In this section, we present the definition and security model of biometric-based remote user authentication. We assume at most n users exist in the system, we denote Π_{ID}^i as a user's i -th session for user authentication, and we denote pid_{ID}^i as the identities of all users recognised by Π_{ID}^i during a session. Let sid_{ID}^i be the unique session identifier with respect to user ID 's i -th session. In particular, $\text{sid}_{ID}^i = \{m_j\}_{j=1}^n$, where

$m_j \in \{0, 1\}^*$ is the message transcript transmitted in the communication channel.

The remote user authentication usually includes three types of roles: users, authentication servers and certification center. For simplicity, we consider a single user and a single authentication server. Generally speaking, user authentication includes two procedures: enrollment and authentication. For biometric-based user authentication, user Alice wishes to authenticate herself to server Bob using biometrics. For user authentication to be successful, Bob needs to ensure that Alice is in possession of her purported biometrics during authentication. We assume there exists a third party, certification center, who is responsible for certifying Alice's biometrics. Specifically, Alice derives a key pair from her biometrics, and the certification center certifies the binding between Alice's identity and her public key (e.g., generating a signature on Alice's identity and public key). For enrollment, Alice will send her identity, public key, and other public information to Bob.

4.1. Definition

A policy-based remote user authentication from multiple biometrics (PBRUA) consists of the following algorithms:

- **Enrollment.** The algorithm is executed between a user and an authentication server. First, the user derives a set of secret values and public sketches $\{(R_i, P_i)\}$ from her multiple biometrics $\{w_i\}$, and generates a set of key pairs $\{(\text{sk}_i, \text{pk}_i)\}$ from her secret values $\{R_i\}$. Second, the user enroll her identity ID , a set of public keys and sketches $\{\text{pk}_i, P_i\}$ to the authentication server. Third, the server generates an authentication policy key according to the enrolled information.
- **Authentication.** This is an interactive algorithm between an enrolled user ID and an authentication server. First, the user derives a set of key pairs $\{(\text{sk}_i, \text{pk}_i)\}$ from her nearby biometrics $\{w'_i\}$ and the enrolled sketches $\{P_i\}$ according to an authentication policy, where $\text{dist}(w_i, w'_i) \leq t$. Second, the user sends a message-signature pair (m, σ) (signed under the derived secret keys), and the derived public keys to the server. Eventually, the authentication server accepts user ID if: 1) the user's authentication policy key is satisfied by the derived public keys; and 2) the message-signature pair is verified as valid under the derived public keys.

4.2. Security Model

Informally, attackers cannot impersonate an authorized user and perform a valid user authentication, even if some of the authorized user's enrolled biometrics are compromised. We assume each user has at most k

enrolled (high or low) biometrics. We define a formal authenticity game between a PPT adversary \mathcal{A} and a challenger \mathcal{S} below.

- **Setup.** \mathcal{S} setups the game for \mathcal{A} by creating n users and an authentication server. For each user, \mathcal{S} chooses a set of distinct biometrics $\{w_i\}$ ($i \in \{1, k\}$), generates a set of secret values and public sketches $\{(R_i, P_i)\}$ from these biometrics, and generates a set of key pairs $\{(\mathbf{sk}_i, \mathbf{pk}_i)\}$. Next, \mathcal{S} generates authentication policy keys dk_i for individual users according to their enrolled public keys. Eventually, \mathcal{S} sends all enrolled users' public information to \mathcal{A} .
- **Training.** \mathcal{A} can make the following queries in an arbitrary sequence to \mathcal{S} .
 - **Send:** If \mathcal{A} issues a send query in the form of (ID, i, m) to simulate a network message for the i -th session of user ID , \mathcal{S} simulates the reaction of instance oracle Π_{ID}^i upon receiving message m , and returns to \mathcal{A} the response that Π_{ID}^i would generate. If \mathcal{A} issues a send query in the form of $(ID', 'start')$, \mathcal{S} creates a new instance oracle $\Pi_{ID'}^i$, and returns to \mathcal{A} the initial protocol message.
 - **Biometrics Reveal:** If \mathcal{A} issues a biometrics reveal query with respect to public sketch P_i , \mathcal{S} returns the enrolled biometrics w_i to \mathcal{A} .
 - **Policy Key Reveal:** If \mathcal{A} issues an authentication policy key reveal query w.r.t. user ID , \mathcal{S} returns user ID 's enrolled policy key dk_i to \mathcal{A} .
- **Challenge.** \mathcal{A} wins the game if all of the following conditions hold.
 1. The server accepts a user ID , meaning that the challenge session sid^s exists.
 2. \mathcal{A} issued neither Policy Key Reveal query w.r.t. user ID , nor Biometrics Reveal queries w.r.t. a set of biometrics that satisfies user ID 's authentication policy key.
 3. $m \in \text{sid}^s$, but there exists no instance oracle Π_{ID}^s which has sent m . Note that m denotes the transcript between user ID and server.

We define the advantage of an adversary \mathcal{A} in the above game is

$$\text{Adv}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\text{Auth}}(\lambda) = \Pr[\mathcal{A} \text{ wins}].$$

DEFINITION 4.1. A PBRUA protocol has user authenticity if for any PPT \mathcal{A} , $\text{Adv}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\text{Auth}}(\lambda)$ is negligible in λ .

Remark. We assume an honest-but-curious authentication server in this work. In this case, the authentication server is assumed to execute the protocol honestly, and try to learn the user's biometrics from the enrolled public information. One restriction is that the authentication server is not allowed to help the attacker to win

the authenticity game. We note that if attackers compromise the user's biometrics w_i , the corresponding secret key \mathbf{sk}_i is revealed. The attackers may generate a nearby w'_i given w_i , and recover \mathbf{sk}_i if $\text{dist}(w_i, w'_i) \leq t$. The attackers may brute force the enrolled biometrics with low-entropy. We also note that this model achieved a strong form of authenticity through biometrics reveal queries. That is, an attacker cannot impersonate a user for authentication using the revealed biometrics, as long as the revealed biometrics do not satisfy the authentication policy.

5. CONSTRUCTION AND ANALYSIS

In this section, we present the proposed construction and its security analysis.

5.1. Construction

The system allows n users to enroll themselves to an authentication server, each user has a k -size set of biometrics $\{w\}$, and server built a database to store all users' enrolled information (we call it reference for convenience). Specifically, a reference includes user's ID , a k -size set of public keys and sketches $\{(\mathbf{pk}, P)\}$, and a decryption key dk (i.e., authentication policy key). In case of user authentication, upon receiving an authentication request from a user ID , the server sends a challenge nonce, an authentication policy Λ and enrolled sketches $\{P\}$ to the user. The user first derives a set of key pairs $\{(\mathbf{sk}, \mathbf{pk})\}$ from her nearby biometrics $\{w'\}$ and enrolled sketches $\{P\}$ according to the authentication policy Λ . Then, the user chooses a response nonce and generates a message-signature pair (m, σ) using a signing key, which aggregates the derived secret keys, where m includes both challenge and response nonce. Eventually, the user generates a ciphertext on the response nonce, which is associated with the derived public keys, sends the ciphertext and signature to the server. Upon receiving the ciphertext and signature from the user, the server decrypts the response nonce using the user ID 's decryption key dk , verifies the message-signature pair (m, σ) using a verification key, which aggregates the derived public keys. In particular, we allow the number of derived public keys to be smaller than the enrolled public keys. The proposed construction consists of the following building blocks.

- A secure fuzzy extractor scheme $\text{FE} = (\text{Gen}, \text{Rep})$.
- A NM-CCA2 secure key-policy attribute based encryption scheme $\text{ABE} = (\text{Setup}, \text{KG}, \text{Enc}, \text{Dec})$.
- An existential unforgeability under chosen message attack (EUF-CMA) secure digital signature scheme $\Sigma = (\text{Setup}, \text{KG}, \text{Sign}, \text{Verify})$.

Below, we use a user Alice and an authentication server Bob to show our proposed construction.

FIGURE 2. Authentication

- **Enrollment.** The authentication server Bob generates a master key pair $(\text{msk}, \text{mpk}) \leftarrow \text{ABE.Setup}(1^\lambda)$. Alice performs the following operations

1. Derive a set of secret/public strings $\{(R_i, P_i) \leftarrow \text{FE.Gen}(w_i)\}$ from a set of biometrics $\{w_i\}$. Note that the public string is also called sketch.
2. Compute a set of key pairs $\{(\text{sk}_i, \text{pk}_i) \leftarrow \Sigma.\text{KG}(\text{mpk}, R_i)\}$, and send $(ID, \{\text{pk}_i, P_i\})$ to Bob.

Upon receiving the enrolled information form Alice, Bob generates a decryption key: $dk \leftarrow \text{ABE.KG}(\Lambda, \text{msk})$ for Alice. Note that Λ denotes an authentication policy, which is shared by all enrolled users.

- **Authentication.** The interaction between Alice and Bob is performed as follows (see Fig. 2).

1. Upon receiving an authentication request from Alice in the form of ID , Bob sends a challenge n_0 , the enrolled sketches $\{P_i\}$, and an authentication policy Λ to Alice.
2. Then, Alice performs the following operations
 - (a) Derive a set of secret values $\{R_i \leftarrow \text{FE.Rep}(w'_i, P_i)\}$ based on the authentication policy Λ , where $\text{dist}(w_i, w'_i) \leq t$.
 - (b) Derive a set of key pairs $\{(\text{sk}_i, \text{pk}_i) \leftarrow \Sigma.\text{KG}(\text{mpk}, R_i)\}$, and denote a set of public keys as $\delta = \{\text{pk}_i\}$.
 - (c) Choose a response nonce n_1 and generate a message-signature pair (m, σ) , where the message is $m = (n_0, n_1)$, the signature $\sigma \leftarrow \Sigma.\text{Sign}(\mathbb{SK}, m)$, and the signing key is $\mathbb{SK} = \sum_{i=1}^{|\delta|} (\text{sk}_i)$.
 - (d) Generate a ciphertext $C \leftarrow \text{ABE.Enc}(\text{mpk}, \delta, n_1)$ and send (σ, C) to Bob, where n_1 is the encrypted message.

3. Bob obtains the response nonce $n_1 \leftarrow \text{ABE.Dec}(\text{mpk}, dk, C)$, and verifies $1 \stackrel{?}{=} \Sigma.\text{Verify}(\mathbb{PK}, m, \sigma)$ under a verification key $\mathbb{PK} = \prod(\text{pk}_i)$. Bob accepts Alice if the signature passes the verification; otherwise, Bob rejects Alice's authentication request.

Remark 1. The enrollment allows each user to enroll various types of biometrics to server Bob, which is executed once. Later, an enrolled user performs user authentication securely using a high-entropy key associated with her multiple biometrics. The user can perform a valid authentication without using some biometrics that are temporarily unavailable (e.g., due to errors) or become weak (e.g., due to ageing). The valid authentication requires that the user's available biometrics satisfy the policy specified by the authentication server at the time of user authentication. If a user enrolls the same set of biometrics to different servers, the user is not required to learn the actual policy of any server before user authentication. Depending on the authentication context, an authentication server can dynamically adjust its authentication policy. The server is assumed to be a trusted party which is responsible for managing authentication policies.

Remark 2. One may notice that the PBRUA can be built from an attribute-based signature (ABS). ABS states that a signer who possesses a set of attributes from an authority can sign a message with a predicate that is satisfied by her attributes [10]. The ABS-based PBRUA contradicts our protocol design because: 1) the user (or signer) must locally store a signing key associated with her attributes set; 2) the authentication server (or authority) must contact the user to update user's signing key as the system evolves; 3) ABS scheme in [10] is not practical compared to the novel combination of KP-ABE [11] and Schnorr signature [12] (we show its practicality in Section 6) because the ABS scheme in [10] relies on certain heavy cryptographic primitives, such as non-interactive zero-knowledge proofs [13]. A revocable ABE scheme [14] can be used to construct the PBRUA if it is necessary to revoke users' biometrics in user authentication. Since the integration of revocable ABE in PBRUA is not too challenging, we leave it to the extended version of this paper.

5.2. Security Analysis

THEOREM 5.1. *The proposed PBRUA achieves user authenticity if the attribute-based encryption scheme ABE is NM-CCA2 secure, and the digital signature scheme Σ is EUF-CMA secure.*

The security of user authenticity is defined by a sequence of games. Game \mathbb{G}_0 is the original user authenticity game. The game \mathbb{G}_1 and game \mathbb{G}_2 are used

to capture the replay attacks and guessing attacks (i.e., guess the challenge session), respectively. In game \mathbb{G}_3 , if adversary can impersonate an honest user by generating a ciphertext which was not previously generated by that user, the challenger can use the generated ciphertext to break the NM-CCA2 security of attribute-based encryption. In game \mathbb{G}_4 , if adversary can impersonate an honest user by forging a digital signature without compromising the set of biometrics which satisfies the user's authentication policy key, the challenger can find a valid forgery in the third message of the protocol, and break the EUF-CMA security of the underlying digital signature. Now, we present the detailed security analysis.

Proof. We define a sequence of games $\{\mathbb{G}_i\}$, and let $\text{Adv}_i^{\text{PBRUA}}$ denote the advantage of the adversary \mathcal{A} in each game \mathbb{G}_i . Assume \mathcal{A} activates at most $m(\lambda)$ sessions in each game.

- \mathbb{G}_0 : This is the original game for user authenticity.
- \mathbb{G}_1 : This game is identical to game \mathbb{G}_0 except that the challenger \mathcal{S} will output a random bit if the server accepts a user ID , but $\text{sid}^i \neq \text{sid}_{ID}^i$. Since n users involved in this game, we have:

$$|\text{Adv}_0^{\text{PBRUA}} - \text{Adv}_1^{\text{PBRUA}}| \leq n \cdot m(\lambda)^2 / 2^\lambda. \quad (1)$$

- \mathbb{G}_2 : This game is identical to game \mathbb{G}_1 except the following difference: \mathcal{S} randomly chooses $g \in [1, m(\lambda)]$ as a guess for the index of the Challenge session. \mathcal{S} will output a random bit if \mathcal{A} 's challenge session does not occur in the g -th session. Therefore we have

$$\text{Adv}_1^{\text{PBRUA}} = m(\lambda) \cdot \text{Adv}_2^{\text{PBRUA}}. \quad (2)$$

- \mathbb{G}_3 : This game is identical to game \mathbb{G}_2 except that in the g -th session, \mathcal{S} outputs a random bit if a **Malle** event happens where \mathcal{A} 's Send query includes a valid ciphertext which was not previously simulated by \mathcal{S} . Then we have

$$|\text{Adv}_2^{\text{PBRUA}} - \text{Adv}_3^{\text{PBRUA}}| \leq \Pr[\text{Malle}]. \quad (3)$$

Let \mathcal{S} denote an attacker against a key-policy attribute based encryption ABE with NM-CCA2 security, who is given a master public key mpk^* , a key generation oracle \mathcal{O}^{KG} , a decryption oracle \mathcal{O}^{Dec} and a ciphertext C^* (associated with a challenge attributes set δ^* and two challenge messages m_0, m_1), aims to break the NM-CCA2 security of ABE. \mathcal{S} simulates the game for \mathcal{A} as follows.

- **Setup**: \mathcal{S} sets up the game for \mathcal{A} by creating n users, each user has a set of biometrics $\{w_i\}$, a set of secret/public strings $\{(R_i, P_i)\}$, and a set of secret/public key pairs $\{\text{sk}_i, \text{pk}_i\}$. \mathcal{S} sets up the master public key of ABE as mpk^* . \mathcal{S} randomly

selects a user ID , and sets up a ciphertext with respect to the user ID at challenge session as C^* . Eventually, \mathcal{F} sends all public keys and public strings (or sketches) to \mathcal{A} .

- **Training**: If \mathcal{A} issues a key generation query associated with an authentication policy Λ_i with the condition that $\Lambda_i(\delta^*) \neq 1$, then \mathcal{S} obtains a decryption key dk_i by invoking the \mathcal{O}^{KG} oracle, and returns it to \mathcal{A} (i.e., policy key reveal query). Meanwhile, if \mathcal{A} issues a decryption query in the form of C_i , then \mathcal{S} obtains a message m_i by invoking the \mathcal{O}^{Dec} oracle, and returns it to \mathcal{A} . Note that \mathcal{S} can honestly answer \mathcal{A} 's biometrics reveal queries, meanwhile, \mathcal{S} can perfectly simulate the message-signature pairs according to the protocol specification.
- When the **Malle** event occurs, i.e., \mathcal{A} outputs $(\text{PK}^*, \sigma^*, C^{*'})$, \mathcal{S} checks whether:
 - * the **Malle** event happens at g -th session w.r.t. user ID ;
 - * the new ciphertext $C^{*'}$ ($C^{*' \neq C^*}$) was not previously simulated by \mathcal{S} ;
 - * verifies $\Sigma.\text{Verify}(\text{PK}^*, f(m_b), \sigma^*) = 1$, where f is a public function and $b \in \{0, 1\}$.

If all the above conditions hold, \mathcal{S} confirms that it as a valid ciphertext from \mathcal{A} , which means that the new ciphertext $C^{*'}$ and the challenge ciphertext C^* have the same encrypted message m_b in the g -th session. To this end, \mathcal{S} can use this ciphertext to break the NM-CCA2 security of ABE. Since at most n users involved in a user authentication, we have

$$|\Pr[\text{Malle}]| \leq n \cdot \text{Adv}_S^{\text{NM-CCA2}}(\lambda). \quad (4)$$

- \mathbb{G}_4 : This game is identical to game \mathbb{G}_3 except that in the g -th session, \mathcal{S} outputs a random bit if a **Forge** event happens where \mathcal{A} 's Send query includes a valid forgery σ^* while user ID 's signing key is not corrupted. Then we have

$$|\text{Adv}_3^{\text{PBRUA}} - \text{Adv}_4^{\text{PBRUA}}| \leq \Pr[\text{Forge}]. \quad (5)$$

Let \mathcal{F} denote a forger against a signature scheme Σ with EUF-CMA security, who is given a public key pk^* and a signing oracle $\mathcal{O}^{\text{Sign}}$, aims to find a forgery σ^* . \mathcal{F} simulates the game for \mathcal{A} as follows.

- **Setup**: \mathcal{F} sets up the game for \mathcal{A} by creating n users, each user has a set of biometrics $\{w_i\}$, a set of secret/public strings $\{(R_i, P_i)\}$, and a decryption key dk . \mathcal{F} sets up the public key of a user ID as pk^* , and generates the remaining secret/public key pairs honestly. \mathcal{F} also honestly generates secret/public key pairs for $n-1$ users. Eventually, \mathcal{F} sends all public information to \mathcal{A} . Below we focus on the simulation of user ID only.

– **Training:** If \mathcal{A} issues a send query in the form of $(\Lambda_i, \{P_i\}, n_0)$ to \mathcal{F} , then \mathcal{F} chooses a response n_1 , and obtains a message-signature pair (m_i, σ_i) from his signing oracle $\mathcal{O}^{\text{Sign}}$, where $m_i = (n_0, n_1)$. Eventually, \mathcal{F} returns (\mathbb{PK}, σ, C) to \mathcal{A} , where $\mathbb{PK} = \text{pk}^* \cdot \prod(\text{pk}_i)$, $\sigma \leftarrow M_\Sigma(\text{mpk}, \text{pk}^*, \sigma_i, \Delta(\text{sk}))$, $\Delta(\text{sk}) = \sum_{i=1}^{|\delta|} (\text{sk}_i)$ and $C \leftarrow \text{ABE.Enc}(\text{mpk}, \delta, n_1)$, $\delta = \{\text{pk}^*, \text{pk}_i, \dots\}$. Since \mathcal{F} chooses the secret/public key pairs $(\text{sk}_i, \text{pk}_i)$, the verification key \mathbb{PK} and signature σ can be simulated by \mathcal{F} due to the linearity of keys and signatures. Meanwhile, it is easy to see that \mathcal{F} can honestly answer \mathcal{A} 's policy key reveal, and biometrics reveal queries with respect to user ID except w_i (otherwise, the simulation aborts).

– When **Forge** event occurs, i.e., \mathcal{A} outputs $(\mathbb{PK}^*, \sigma^*, C^*)$, and both the verification key \mathbb{PK}^* and the derived public key set δ^* are associated with pk^* , \mathcal{F} checks whether:

- * the **Forge** event happens at g -th session;
- * the challenge ciphertext C^* is decrypted by using the decryption key of user ID ;
- * the message-signature pair (m^*, σ^*) was not previously simulated by \mathcal{S} ;
- * verifies $\Sigma.\text{Verify}(\mathbb{PK}^*, m^*, \sigma^*) = 1$.

If all the above conditions hold, \mathcal{F} confirms that it is a successful forgery from \mathcal{A} , then \mathcal{F} extracts the forgery via $\sigma^* \leftarrow M_\Sigma(\text{mpk}, \text{pk}^*, \sigma^*, \Delta(\text{sk}))$ due to the homomorphic property of Σ , where $\Delta(\text{sk})$ is derived from a set of secret/public strings $\{R_i, P_i\}$ which is associated with the derived public key set δ^* . To this end, \mathcal{F} outputs σ^* as its own forgery; Otherwise, \mathcal{F} aborts the game. Since at most n users, and k -size public keys are involved in a user authentication, we have

$$|\Pr[\text{Forge}]| \leq n \cdot k \cdot \text{Adv}_{\mathcal{F}}^{\text{EUF-CMA}}(\lambda). \quad (6)$$

In game \mathbb{G}_4 , \mathcal{A} has no advantage. By combining the above results together, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Adv}_{\mathcal{A}}^{\text{PBRUA}}(\lambda) &\leq n \cdot m(\lambda)^2 / 2^\lambda + m(\lambda) \cdot n \\ &\quad \cdot [\text{Adv}_{\mathcal{S}}^{\text{NM-CCA2}}(\lambda) \\ &\quad + k \cdot \text{Adv}_{\mathcal{F}}^{\text{EUF-CMA}}(\lambda)]. \end{aligned}$$

□

6. INSTANTIATION

In this section, we start with discussing the choice of primitives to construct a practical instantiation. Then, we present the concrete construction.

6.1. Selecting Suitable Primitives

- *Selecting Fuzzy Extractor.* To find an efficient fuzzy extractor, we rely on a digital locker-based

reusable fuzzy extractor [15], which is proven to be computationally secure in the random oracle model. The digital locker is a symmetric encryption scheme that tolerates correlated and weak (i.e., non-uniform) keys [16]. In particular, digital locker requires that obtaining any information about the plaintext from the ciphertext is as hard as guessing the key.

The digital locker includes lock and unlock algorithms. The lock algorithm is used to lock a value val using a key key : $c = \text{lock}(\text{key}, \text{val})$. The unlock algorithm is $\text{val} = \text{unlock}(\text{key}, c)$, which means it either outputs val if key is correct, or \perp with high probability (i.e., the wrong key can be identified) [17]. To initiate a digital locker, we choose a cryptographic hash function \mathbb{H} (modelled as a random oracle). We allow the locking algorithm $\text{lock}(\text{key}, \text{val})$ to output a pair $(\text{nonce}, \mathbb{H}(\text{nonce}, \text{key}) \oplus (\text{val} || 0^\lambda))$, where nonce is a nonce, and λ is the security parameter. In particular, “ $||0^\lambda$ ” is used to ensure the unlock algorithm can tell (with certainty $1 - 2^{-\lambda}$) when the correct value is unlocked.

- *Selecting Attribute-based Encryption.* To find a practical ABE scheme, we rely on the Fast Attribute-based Message Encryption scheme: FAME [11]. FAME supports unbounded ABE universes, has no restriction on the monotone policies used, has constant-time decryption, is adaptively secure in the random oracle model under standard decisional linear assumption [18], and is based on the asymmetric prime-order Type-III pairing. We stress that the asymmetric prime-order pairing is the most efficient one. A detailed comparison between the state-of-the-art ABE schemes can be found in [11].

- *Selecting Digital Signature.* We choose the Schnorr signature scheme to instantiate the underlying digital signatures. This is because Schnorr signature has a desired homomorphic property regarding signing keys and signatures, which can be used to “aggregate” the derived key pairs for saving the communication overhead [19]. Alternatively, the Waters’ identity-based signature scheme [20] is also suitable. Both discrete logarithm-based and identity-based signature schemes can be used in PBRUA.

6.2. Instantiation

We define a pseudo-random generator as $\mathbb{G} : \mathbb{G}_T \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^*$. We employ two collision-resistant hash functions $\mathbb{H} : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_q$, $\mathbb{H}' : \{0, 1\}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{G}$, and the size of hash output \mathbb{H} is assumed to be l . We assume the biometrics w is a source with α -entropy and k -samples if $\tilde{\mathbb{H}}_\infty(w_{j_1}, \dots, w_{j_k} | j_1, \dots, j_k) \geq \alpha$, where $\tilde{\mathbb{H}}_\infty$ means the average minentropy of w_{j_1}, \dots, w_{j_k} given j_1, \dots, j_k . Let lock and unlock be a $\tilde{\ell}$ -composable secure digital locker with error γ . There are two types of inputs to hash function \mathbb{H}' . One is (y, ℓ, t) , the other is (j, ℓ, t) ,

where y is an arbitrary string, j is a positive integer, $\ell \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ and $t \in \{1, 2\}$. We denote $y\ell t$ and $0j\ell t$ to represent these two inputs. Let $\widehat{e} : \mathbb{G} \times \mathbb{H} \rightarrow \mathbb{G}_T$ be an asymmetric bilinear maps.

• **Enrollment.** The authentication server takes a security parameter λ as input, outputs a master public key $\text{mpk} = (g, h, H_1, H_2, T_1, T_2)$, and a master secret key $\text{msk} = (a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, g^{d_1}, g^{d_2}, g^{d_3})$, where $(a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2) \in \mathbb{Z}_q^*$, $(d_1, d_2, d_3) \in \mathbb{Z}_q$, $H_1 = h^{a_1}$, $H_2 = h^{a_2}$, $T_1 = \widehat{e}(g, h)^{d_1 \cdot a_1 + d_3}$, $T_2 = \widehat{e}(g, h)^{d_2 \cdot a_2 + d_3}$. On the user side, an enrolled user performs the following operations

1. Select a biometrics $w_i \in \{0, 1\}^{16}$ (the source w_i is 16-bit long, the Hamming error is $t = 2$), and choose a secret value $R_i \in \{0, 1\}^{30}$.
2. For $i \in \{1, \dots, 589\}$ (the value $\widehat{\ell} \approx n^c \cdot \log(2/\widehat{\delta}) : 16^2 \cdot \log(2/0.01) \approx 589$, where $n = 16$ is the length of biometrics, $c = 2$ is a constant value, $\widehat{\delta} = 0.01$ is the fuzzy extractor [15]'s allowable error parameter, and γ is small enough so that $\widehat{\ell} \cdot \gamma \leq \widehat{\delta}/2$):
 - (a) Choose uniformly random $j_{i,k} \in [1, 16]$.
 - (b) Set $v_i = w_{j_{i,1}}, \dots, w_{j_{i,k}}$.
 - (c) Set $c_i = \text{lock}(v_i, R_i)$, i.e., $c_i = \text{H}(v_i) \oplus (R_i || 0^{l-30})$.
 - (d) Set $p_i = c_i, (j_{i,1}, \dots, j_{i,k})$.
3. Set (R_i, P_i) , where $R_i \in \{0, 1\}^{30}$, and $P_i = (p_1, \dots, p_{589})$.
4. Compute $\text{sk}_i = \text{H}(R_i)$ and $\text{pk}_i = g^{\text{sk}_i}$.

The enrolled user repeats the above procedure up to k times, and sends $(ID, \{\text{pk}_i, P_i\})$ to the server.

Based on the enrolled information, the server generates a decryption key associated with an authentication policy (\mathbf{M}, π) (\mathbf{M} has n_1 rows and n_2 columns, and n_1 covers the enrolled public keys $\{\text{pk}_i\}$): $dk_i = (sk_0, sk_1, \dots, sk_{n_1})$, where $(r_1, r_2) \in \mathbb{Z}_q^*$, $sk_0 = (h^{b_1 \cdot r_1}, h^{b_2 \cdot r_2}, h^{r_1 + r_2})$, $\sigma'_2, \dots, \sigma'_{n_2} \in \mathbb{Z}_q$, $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, n_1\}, \sigma_i \in \mathbb{Z}_q$ and $t = \{1, 2\} : sk_{i,t} = \text{H}'(\pi(i)1t)^{b_1 \cdot r_1 / a_t} \cdot \text{H}'(\pi(i)2t)^{b_2 \cdot r_2 / a_t} \cdot \text{H}'(\pi(i)3t)^{(r_1 + r_2) / a_t} \cdot g^{\sigma_i / a_t} \cdot (g^{d_t})^{\mathbf{M}(i,1)} \cdot \prod_{j=2}^{n_2} [\text{H}'(0j1t)^{b_1 \cdot r_1 / a_t} \cdot \text{H}'(0j2t)^{b_2 \cdot r_2 / a_t} \cdot \text{H}'(0j3t) \cdot g^{\sigma'_j / a_t}]^{\mathbf{M}(i,j)}$, $sk_{i,3} = g^{-\sigma_i} \cdot (g^{d_3})^{\mathbf{M}(i,1)} \cdot \prod_{j=2}^{n_2} (g^{-\sigma'_j})^{\mathbf{M}(i,j)}$. Let $sk_i = (sk_{i,1}, sk_{i,2}, sk_{i,3})$. We note that the master secret key used in the decryption key dk_i is (a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2) , and the server chooses $(r_1, r_2, \sigma'_2, \dots, \sigma'_{n_2}, \sigma_i)$ for the enrolled user.

• **Authentication.** If an enrolled user ID received a challenge nonce n_0 , the enrolled sketches $\{P_i\}$, and an authentication policy from the server, the user performs the following operations

- Derive a set of secret/public key pairs $\{(\text{sk}_i, \text{pk}_i)\}$, where each key pair is computed as follows
 1. Choose a biometrics $w'_i \in \{0, 1\}^{16}$ with at most 2 bits flipped.
 2. For $i \in \{1, \dots, 589\}$:
 - (a) Set $v'_i = w'_{j_{i,1}}, \dots, w'_{j_{i,k}}$ based on the values $(j_{i,1}, \dots, j_{i,k})$ in the public strings p_i .
 - (b) Compute $R_i = \text{unlock}(v'_i, c_i)$, i.e., $R_i || 0^{l-30} = c_i \oplus \text{H}(v'_i)$.
 - (c) Output R_i if $R_i \neq \perp$ and last $l - 30$ bit of $R_i || 0^{l-30}$ is "0".
 3. Compute $\text{sk}_i = \text{H}(R_i)$, $\text{pk}_i = g^{\text{sk}_i}$, and let $\delta = \{\text{pk}_i\}$.
- Choose a response nonce n_1 , and generate a message-signature pair $(m, \sigma) = (m, g^{esk}, s = esk + \text{SK} \cdot e)$, where $esk \in \mathbb{Z}_q, e = \text{H}(m), m = (n_0, n_1)$, and $\text{SK} = \sum_{i=1}^{|\delta|} (\text{sk}_i)$.
- Generate a ciphertext on nonce n_1 : $C = (ct_0, \{ct_y\}_{y \in \delta}, ct')$, and send (σ, C) to the server, where $s_1, s_2 \in \mathbb{Z}_q, ct_0 = (H_1^{s_1}, H_2^{s_2}, h^{s_1 + s_2}), \forall y \in \delta$ and $\ell \in \{1, 2, 3\}$: $ct_{y,\ell} = \text{H}(y\ell 1)^{s_1} \cdot \text{H}(y\ell 2)^{s_2}$, $ct' = \text{G}(T_1^{s_1} \cdot T_2^{s_2}) \oplus n_1$.

The authentication server runs the following steps to obtain the encrypted nonce n_1 . If the set of public keys $\delta = \{\text{pk}_i\}$ satisfies the MSP (\mathbf{M}, π) , then there exists constants $\{\gamma_i\}_{i \in I}$ that satisfy the equation in Section 3.2. It computes $n_1 = ct' \oplus \text{G}(B/A) = ct' \oplus \text{G}(T_1^{s_1} \cdot T_2^{s_2})$, where A and B are described below (the detailed correctness is referred to [11]). Note that $sk_{(0,1)}, sk_{(0,2)}, sk_{(0,3)}$ denote the first, second and third element of sk_0 , and the same rule applies to ct_0 .

$$A = \widehat{e}\left(\prod_{i \in I} sk_{(i,1)}^{\gamma_i}, ct_{(0,1)}\right) \cdot \widehat{e}\left(\prod_{i \in I} sk_{(i,2)}^{\gamma_i}, ct_{(0,2)}\right) \cdot \widehat{e}\left(\prod_{i \in I} sk_{(i,3)}^{\gamma_i}, ct_{(0,3)}\right)$$

$$B = \widehat{e}\left(\prod_{i \in I} ct_{(\pi(i),1)}^{\gamma_i}, sk_{(0,1)}\right) \cdot \widehat{e}\left(\prod_{i \in I} ct_{(\pi(i),2)}^{\gamma_i}, sk_{(0,2)}\right) \cdot \widehat{e}\left(\prod_{i \in I} ct_{(\pi(i),3)}^{\gamma_i}, sk_{(0,3)}\right)$$

In the end, the server verifies $g^s \stackrel{?}{=} g^{esk} \cdot \text{PK}^{\text{H}(m)}$, where $m = (n_0, n_1), \text{PK} = \prod_{i=1}^{|\delta|} (\text{pk}_i)$.

7. EVALUATION

In this section, we provide the implementation and evaluation analysis. The implementation runs on a Ubuntu desktop with 3.6 GHz Inter Core i7 processor and 1.9 GB memory. We assume a user's biometric data is converted into binary strings (i.e., Hamming distance) due to the input requirement of reusable fuzzy extractor [15]. We use a simulated data with a uniform

distribution as the input of fuzzy extractor.⁵ We analyze the proposed instantiation in terms of storage cost, communication overhead, and running time. We assume an identity is 256-bit and a biometrics source is 16-bit. SHA-256 is a hash function with 256-bit output. The proof-of-concept implementation is available on GitHub [23].

- *Storage Cost.* Let $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{Z}_q}$ denote the length of an element in \mathbb{Z}_q , and let k denote the number of enrolled biometrics. Since the number of public strings in a sketch is $\hat{\ell} = 589$, the length of a reference is calculated as:

$$\text{Reference} = ID + \{(pk, P)\} + dk = 256 + k[\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{Z}_q} + 589(256 + 16)] + 2[3(k + 1)\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{Z}_q}].$$

where 2 is associated with the decryption key dk of ABE, because an asymmetric Type-III pairing is used in the experiment. The storage cost of our proposed instantiation for each user is linear to the number of enrolled biometrics, and the overall storage cost at the server side is linear to the number of enrolled users.

- *Communication Overhead.* The length of a transmitted nonce is $\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{Z}_q}$, the length of a transmitted authentication policy is \mathcal{L}_Λ , and the XOR technique is used in the encryption and decryption of ABE.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Overhead} &= ID + \Lambda + \{P\} + n_0 + \sigma + C \\ &= 256 + \mathcal{L}_\Lambda + k[589(256 + 16)] + 256 \\ &\quad + 6(k + 1)\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{Z}_q} + 3\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{Z}_q} \\ &= 512 + 160208k + 6(k + 1)\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{Z}_q} \\ &\quad + \mathcal{L}_\Lambda + 3\mathcal{L}_{\mathbb{Z}_q}. \end{aligned}$$

The communication overhead between a user and a server during user authentication is linear to the number of enrolled biometrics, since the enrolled public sketches are required to send back for user authentication. The signing/verification key pair involving in a message-signature pair is a constant value, due to the homomorphic property of the Schnorr signature scheme.

- *Selecting Suitable Biometrics.* Biometrics is mainly categorized as physiological and behavioural traits. The physiological traits include but are not limited to fingerprint, palm-print, face, finger-vein, iris and DNA, while the behavioural traits include but are not limited to speech, gait and keystroke. Since there is no single biometrics can meet all the requirements of user authentications, the selection of biometrics should consider several factors, such as entropy, measurability, acceptability. Entropy means that

TABLE 2. A comparative summary of widely used biometrics.

Trait/Feature:	Entropy	Measure	Accept
Fingerprint	Low	High	High
Speech	Low	Medium	High
Palm-print	Medium	High	Medium
Face	Low	High	High
Finger-vein	High	Low	Low
Iris	Low	High	High
Retina	High	Low	Low
DNA	High	Low	Low
Gait	Medium	Low	Medium

the biometrics trait should be sufficiently unique to one another, which in turn affects false rejection rate (i.e., the system fails to recognize an authorized user and rejects the user as an impostor) and false acceptance rate (i.e., an unauthorized user is being identified as an authorized user). Measurability means the ease of measurement or acquisition of the trait. Acceptability means whether the individuals are willing to have their biometric traits captured and assessed. Now, we provide a comparative summary on the widely used biometrics in Table 2, and the selection of multiple biometrics is mainly dependent on the context of user authentications. We use High, Medium and Low to evaluate these factors.

For simplicity, we consider two types of user authentication: everyday authentication and high-security one. Using multiple biometrics for everyday authentication may be cumbersome. However, for high-security operations such as border control, they become more desirable. Now we show an example of selecting suitable biometrics from Table 2 for border control. We assume the policy's format is $(A \wedge B) \vee (C \wedge D)$, which is described in Section 1. Let $Index_{0/1}$ denote the left/right index figure, and let $Iris_{0/1}$ denote the left/right iris. An authentication server may generate a policy as: $(Index_0 \wedge Iris_1) \vee (Iris_0 \wedge Index_1)$. The policy may be updated over time in various contexts, such as requiring retina to replace iris.

- *Selecting Suitable Policies.* It is undesired when an authentication policy fills with all AND gates (or all OR gates) because it affects the usability/security of the system. We note that the underlying fuzzy extractor may fail to recover the same string R with a small probability (e.g., 0.01). Therefore, the authentication policy with all AND gates reduces the *usability* of the system, since a single failure of the fuzzy extractor invalids the user authentication from multiple biometrics. We discover that the fuzzy extractors cannot guarantee that they recover secret values $\{R\}$ with 100% probability. This is because the noise level in measured biometrics may exceed the allowed limit of the fuzzy extractors. On the other hand, the authentication policy with all OR gates is

⁵One may consider other metric spaces such as set difference [21], and edit distance [6]. The uniform source may be replaced by a non-uniform one such as symbol-fixing source [22].

not secure if one of the biometrics is compromised or under low-entropy attack.

We use examples to show the importance of selecting suitable policies for authentication. Suppose that a user has four enrolled biometrics: A, B, C and D , and we assume the authentication server will not choose three AND gates or three OR gates to generate an authentication policy due to the trade-off between security and usability. For example, the possible authentication policies could have either one OR gate or two OR gates, which include but are not limited to: $\Lambda_0 = (A \wedge C) \vee (B \vee D)$, $\Lambda_1 = (A \wedge C) \wedge (B \vee D)$, $\Lambda_2 = (A \wedge C) \vee (B \wedge D)$, and $\Lambda_3 = (A \vee C) \wedge (B \vee D)$. In addition, we evaluate the accuracy of user authentication under various number of OR gates. As shown in Figure 3 (left, with red line), the desired authentication policy with four biometrics is Λ_3 , which includes two OR gates. We choose MNT224 curve [24] to perform pairing operations in the user authentication under each authentication policy up to 500 times, and we choose the worst case for benchmarking.

Suppose that a user has eight enrolled biometrics, and the potential authentication policies with four OR gates or three OR gates include but are not limited to: $\Lambda'_0 = [(A \wedge C) \wedge (B \vee D)] \vee [(E \wedge G) \vee (F \vee H)]$, $\Lambda'_1 = [(A \wedge C) \vee (B \vee D)] \vee [(E \wedge G) \wedge (F \vee H)]$, $\Lambda'_2 = [(A \wedge C) \vee (B \wedge D)] \wedge [(E \wedge G) \vee (F \vee H)]$, and $\Lambda'_3 = [(A \wedge C) \wedge (B \vee D)] \wedge [(E \wedge G) \vee (F \vee H)]$. Similarly, we evaluate its accuracy under the number of OR gates. As shown in Figure 3 (left, with grey line), the 100% accuracy can be achieved if four OR gates are involved in an authentication policy. Besides, the eight biometrics-based user authentication system has more desired authentication policies.

FIGURE 3. In Figure (left), the red and grey line denote the accuracy of our scheme with respect to four and eight biometrics (i.e., Bio_4 and Bio_8), respectively. In Figure (right), we evaluate our scheme using three different curves.

To conclude, an authentication server may fine-tune authentication policies to control the trade-off between security (or false acceptance) and usability (or false rejection). The security of user authentication can be enhanced by using more AND

gates in user authentication policies, and the usability of user authentication can be elevated by using more OR gates in user authentication policies.

- *Computational Cost.* The number of biometrics is assumed to be $k = 8$ (k could be a various value), and the authentication policy is in the form of $\Lambda = [(A \wedge C) \wedge (B \wedge D)] \wedge [(E \wedge G) \wedge (F \wedge H)]$ (i.e., the most costly case) which means 8 biometrics are required for decryption [25]. Since bilinear map is the most heavy operation and there exists a number of candidate Elliptic curves, we choose three kinds of curves in the Pairing-Based Cryptography library to evaluate the user authentication, including MNT159, MNT224 (Type-III pairings) [24], and BN254 (Type-II pairing) [26] (see Figure 3 (right)). For example, if we use MNT159 curve, then a user spends 20ms to authenticate herself to a server, under certain authentication policies such as Λ'_1 or Λ'_2 (i.e., with three or four OR gates).
- *A Case Study.* Assuming users are required to register three types of biometrics, including fingerprints, face, and iris in certain authentication scenario such as border control. Further assume that the authentication server provides three authentication policies $\Lambda_1 = (\text{Index}_0 \wedge \text{Iris}_1) \wedge (\text{Iris}_0 \vee \text{Face})$, $\Lambda_2 = (\text{Index}_0 \wedge \text{Iris}_1) \vee (\text{Iris}_0 \wedge \text{Index}_1)$, $\Lambda_3 = (\text{Index}_0 \vee \text{Iris}_1) \wedge (\text{Iris}_0 \vee \text{Index}_1)$, as described in the Bio_4 setting. Users may choose to use any of the authentication policies for authentication.

The security of user authentication performed in this way is featured by using at least two biometrics for satisfying those policies. The usability in this case is featured by the flexibility of choosing any of the three policies for performing user authentication. For example, if a user wears a face mask, she may choose authentication policy Λ_2 or Λ_3 . If a user wears a glove, she may choose authentication policy Λ_1 .

8. RELATED WORK

Biometrics information can be used in user authentication systems. For instance, Fan and Lin [27] introduced a three-factor-based (e.g., smart card, password, and biometrics) user authentication. The user relies on a keyed function (e.g., a secret string is used to encrypt biometrics) to ensure biometric privacy, and the authentication server performs biometric matching (i.e., find a user's enrolled information from the database and make a decision) in the encrypted domain. Similarly, Huang et al. [28] used the Paillier cryptosystem [29] as encryption primitive to hide user's biometrics. They proposed a flexible framework of biometrics-based identification. Specifically, they use a garbled circuit [30] to efficiently and obliviously perform biometric matching and retrieve an authentication result. In this work, we focus on user authentication with biometrics privacy.

Fuzzy extractor (FE) has been widely used in designing biometric-based user authentications [31, 32, 33]. For example, Juels and Wattenberg [34] introduced a cryptography primitive called fuzzy commitment. It can be used in the biometric-based authentication systems, since its error-correcting technique can correct certain errors within a suitable metric (e.g., Hamming distance). Dodis et al. [6] formalized the notions of secure sketches and fuzzy extractors. In particular, they provided concrete constructions of secure sketches and FEs in three metrics (i.e., Hamming distance, set difference, and edit distance), and the constructions are information-theoretically secure.

Boyer [31] introduced reusable fuzzy extractor for user authentication, such that FE remains secure even if a user generates multiple secret/public string pairs using the same biometrics w in the enrollment phase (i.e., $\{(R_i, P_i)\} \leftarrow \text{Gen}(w)$). To remove an assumption on the correlation between multiple readings of biometrics, Canetti et al. [15] proposed an efficient and reusable FE that can handle biometrics whose entropy rate is lower than its error rate. The proposed scheme is proven computationally secure in the random oracle model. Since a user may enroll herself in various authentication servers in real-life applications, the reusable FEs are suitable for our proposed PBRUA. We stress that the concern on security (or source distribution) of reusable FEs is beyond the scope of this work.

Multi-biometric cryptosystems have been studied [35, 3, 4]. These user authentications rely on a fusion strategy to manage multiple biometrics during authentication, which can be either AND or OR gates. For example, Chatterjee et al. [36] introduced a primitive called multi-sketch. The idea is, each user registers a set of distinct biometrics $\mathbf{w} = \{w_1, \dots, w_k\}$ to a database \mathcal{F} , and registers the corresponding set of sketches $\{P\}$ to another database \mathcal{I} . A user can recover \mathbf{w} from sketches $\{P\}$ and from a new biometrics reading $\bar{\mathbf{w}} = \{w'_1, \dots, w'_k\}$ if a certain number of biometrics match between the two sets $(\mathbf{w}, \bar{\mathbf{w}})$ (in terms of set difference [6]). The recovered biometrics \mathbf{w} can be used to generate high-entropy keys for user authentication. In particular, ten fingerprints were used to show the feasibility of multi-sketch in practice. We identify the following differences between multi-sketch and PBRUA. First, PBRUA supports fine-grained biometric matching with both AND and OR gates. However, the biometric matching of multi-sketch supports a single threshold gate. It is clear that any matching policy based on a single threshold gate can be converted to a policy using AND and OR gates; however, it is not true that any policy based on AND and OR gates can be expressed by a single threshold gate. Second, the matching accuracy of multi-sketch depends on the number of enrolled users. Loosely speaking, the more enrolled users in the system, the more accurate is a multi-sketch scheme. The matching accuracy of

TABLE 3. The comparison between various biometric-based (remote) solutions.

Features/Schemes	[31]	[27]	[28]	[33]	[4]	[36]	[37]	Ours
FE-based	✓	×	×	✓	×	✓	✓	✓
Single-factor	✓	×	✓	✓	×	✓	✓	✓
Multi-biometrics	×	×	×	×	✓	✓	✓	✓
Fine-grained	×	×	×	×	✓	×	×	✓

PBRUA is independent of the number of enrolled users. It is controlled by adjusting authentication policies on each enrolled user’s multiple biometrics.

Uzun et al. [37] proposed a fuzzy extractor-based remote user authentication scheme. They applied hash functions to the recovered secrets, designed to be compatible with password-based user authentications. For example, the user can send the hash of the recovered secret and password (i.e., $H(\text{secret}||\text{password})$) to the server for authentications. Since our design goal focuses on biometrics-based user authentication, we use digital signature-based user authentication, fuzzy extractor to handle the noisy biometrics, and ABE to manage multiple biometrics. Our scheme is generic and secure because: 1) our scheme can handle various biometrics, while [37] is limited to face and voice. 2) [37] suffers replay attacks as attackers eavesdropping on the communication channel can impersonate a user successfully by replaying the transmitted messages between the client and server. Their remote authentication protocol does not involve any nonce or random numbers in user authentication. In comparison, our proposed scheme is immune to such attacks. Since the security and usability requirements are various in real-life applications, one can apply either multi-biometrics or two-factor (password and biometrics) to user authentications. The advantage of PBRUA is, we allow the authentication server to balance the security and usability of user authentication system via fine-tuned authentication policies.

Table 3 shows a comparison between various kinds of biometric-based (remote) user authentications. Single-factor means that user’s (or multiple) biometrics is the only factor to determine valid authentication. Fine-grained means AND and OR gate are involved in the biometric matching. In this work, we rely on the user’s biometrics alone to secure user authentication. The use of hardware tokens [38] and FIDO [39] together are beyond the scope of this work. The proposed PBRUA supports a flexible and fine-grained biometric matching. It can fine-tune authentication policies among multiple biometrics to control the trade-off between security and usability. To the best of our knowledge, our is the first attempt to use attribute-based encryption to manage multiple biometrics for user authentications.

9. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed the first generic framework of remote user authentication from multiple biometrics

based on the fuzzy extractor and attribute-based encryption, to enhance both the security and usability in biometrics-based authentication systems. The proposed framework achieves user authenticity against any third party who attempts to impersonate an authorized user, and supports flexible user authentication as the security and usability of the authentication system could be changed in different contexts. In particular, the instantiation of the proposed framework is practical, which was confirmed by the comprehensive evaluation. We leave the construction of multi-biometric-based remote user authentication with privacy considerations as our future work. The future work will conceal the correlation between user’s identity and their multiple biometric templates [36]. The goal is to prevent attackers from learning the set of biometric data at the server side that belongs to the same user during user authentications.

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11. DATA AVAILABILITY

The data underlying this article will be shared on reasonable request to the corresponding author.

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